

Religious Education in a Multicultural Village: A Case Study of Pancasila Village, District of Lamongan, East Java, Indonesia

Sutiah Sutiah

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the effect of the introduction of religious education into a multicultural village, with reform of the village through the Islamic educational system being a main lesson at secondary school level. Besides the issues which relate to curriculum enrichment through religious content, the aim of this change is to support multiculturalism and intercultural communication to achieve tolerance, democratic dialogue, respect for each other, togetherness, and social development. This research was a qualitative research to understand a phenomenon in the social context naturally with the advanced process of interaction between researchers' in-depth communication and the phenomenon. Subject of research was the researchers, while the research object was the Multicultural Education Implementation of current and forthcoming. The methods of data collection were interviews, observation, and documentation. Data analysis technique was interactive analysis techniques as disclosed by Miles and Huberman which included four steps, namely, data collection, data reduction, data display, and conclusion. The results showed that the implementation of Religious Education in a Multicultural Village at Educational curricula with an interactive basis and dialogue from religious education have the same analytical view of culture and religious methodology and reflect the same as approach through multicultural education or interculture. The conclusion of this research that religious education which uses the interactive method on a problem basis can make a direct contribution to intercultural education and promote social cohesion.

Introduction

Indonesia is well known as a complex society with a multicultural structure. Pluralism in the country can mostly be seen from the religious aspect, with religion being the cause of the birth of multiculturalism. The increase of pluralism in society, together with social and ethnic demands for rights, need appropriate educational policy, which until now has been ignored. Multiculturalism in neither a choice or something which can be avoided by society. But, variety of multiculturalism mentions need to manage proportionally (Nye, 2007).

The relationship between religion and multiculturalism is complex, depending on the definition of the concepts and social context in which it occurs (Williams, 2015). Multicultural education is considering the community as a variety of individuals with different ethnic groups religions, genders, and social classes. Individual variety in society is shown in the variety of students who attend educational academy (Banks, 1989). The process of religious fulfilment can cause dynamic and social mobilisation which lead to strained situations and conflict, such as conflict between upper and lower classes or in government policy on society. Horizontal characteristic of group such as inter-religious groups, inter-ethnic groups, and inter-political party groups. The need to include the variety of religions in multicultural education is strengthened by the turmoil which has been caused by multi-ethnicity. The phenomena of religious radicalism and violent acts on the pretext of religion have risen in the last decade; for example, the first and second Bali terror bombings, another terror bombing at the Australian embassy, and the JW Mariott bombing give impact to group stigma and religious life Actions committed by group organizations acting on behalf of religion are creating more and more uneasiness. (Parekh, 2000) reporting about the future of England multiethnicity which interest by using religious category in leftwing and rightwing propaganda which spread in England. Include the document that proclaim the government to use the army to ease all mosque, temple, and synagogues (Runnymede, 2000).

Religious education (RE) in schools is a form of non-denominational religious teaching with moral and civilian goals (Jackson, 2004). Igrave (2001) conducted research on the influence of children with Muslim, Hindu and Christian backgrounds in a multicultural primary school in Leicester, by developing an RE-based research process approach. His pedagogy took advantage of children's readiness to harness the religion encountered through interaction with other children in school. Teachers often act as facilitators, encouraging and clarifying

questions, and can be triggers for students, who are considered as collaborators in the teaching and learning process. Ipgrave found that an approach with RE enhances children's self-esteem, provides an opportunity to develop skills, enabling underachievers to express themselves, and shapes the climate of their environment (Jackson, 2003, 2004). Teaching religious education in this way is an opportunity to observe the influence of different cultures. With appropriate general religious education, students can have a formal place and ask questions and discuss issues in depth. It is considered that children cannot handle the explanation of plurality obtained from outside school. We ultimately ignore their capacity for open-mindedness (Measham, 2014).

Indonesia is not an Islamic country, but it is strictly religious. The first principle of Pancasila, the state ideology, is belief in one God. The 1945 Constitution guarantees freedom of religion, but not freedom of non-religion. Indonesia only recognizes six religions: Islam, Protestantism, Catholicism, Hinduism, Buddhism and Confucianism. All citizens must identify with one of these six religions on their identity card and in many official documents, such as birth and marriage certificates.

However, there are also stories about students from minority religions who have had change school or even move home to other cities, because schools are not willing to provide teachers for minority groups. It may be expensive for schools to provide one or two students with special teachers, and some schools do not comply with this rule. The approach to teaching religion in a public school is an "in religion", or recognition approach. The curriculum for each religion emphasizes the doctrine and morals of that religion. However, according to the curriculum, students of all religions must study consistently, from primary school to high school, the notion of "tolerance, and maintaining harmony in private and social life" (Tan, 2008). They must learn to be "steadfast in the face of challenges, obstacles, and changes that arise in social interaction, in the local, national, regional and global environment". Some of these universities UIN Maulana Malik Ibrahim Indonesia produce a generation of political, academic, economic, and social leaders of Indonesia. It is heartening that at least some of their students are encouraged to learn to live in harmony with people of other faiths.

Islam education is a container for the transfer of Islamic values, at least placed in a wise position against the conditions of society around them (local wisdom). It provides guidance to people who are still considered to be wrong by the religion. The focus of this research is consideration of the role of Islamic education in the formation of a multicultural society, and the process of solving the problem of such a role in Pancasila Village, Turi, Lamongan, East Java. It also discusses how to make the curriculum of Islamic education strategic to ensure Islamic values are well embedded, true to the Muslims and perceived them goodness as well as its benefits as a religion of mercy for other people outside of Islam. The purpose of the research is to strengthen the theory of multicultural education in developing civil society, the curriculum diversity based on cultural diversity, and the theory of communal society (communal theory). The second purpose is the fact that religious education provides individuals understanding to those who are religious with multicultural. Previous studies have made clearer difference between the responsibilities of religious (the fostering of religious faith) and that of religious education in contributing to a significant perception on the scenery of religion at different cultural condition.

Literature Review

Religious Education

Religious education is the teaching of a particular religion (although in the United Kingdom the term religious instruction would refer to the teaching of a particular religion, with religious education referring to teaching about religions in general) and its varied aspects: its beliefs, doctrines, rituals, customs, rites, and personal roles. In Western and secular culture, religious education implies a type of education which is largely separate from academia, and which (generally) regards religious belief as a fundamental tenet and operating modality, as well as a prerequisite for attendance. This kind of religious education has drawn criticism because, it is argued, there is no neutral perspective from which to study religions and any kind of compulsory schooling is likely to impact on the formation of a student's religious identity (Moulin, 2015).

People oppose religious education in public schools on various grounds. One is that it constitutes a state sponsorship or establishment of whatever religious beliefs are taught. Others argue that if a particular religion is taught in school, children who do not belong to that religion will either feel pressure to conform or be excluded from their peers. Proponents argue that religious beliefs have historically socialized people's behavior and morality. They feel that teaching religion in school is important to encourage children to be responsible, spiritually sound adults (Jackson, 2012).

Pancasila and Multiculturalism

The Republic of Indonesia, the world's fourth most populous nation, has 203 million people living on nearly one thousand permanently settled islands. Some two-to-three hundred ethnic groups with their own languages and dialects range in population from the Javanese (about 70 million) and Sundanese (about 30 million) on Java, to peoples numbering in the thousands on remote islands. The nature of Indonesian national culture is somewhat analogous to that of India—multicultural, rooted in older societies and interethnic relations, and developed in twentieth century nationalist struggles against a European imperialism that nonetheless forged that nation and

many of its institutions. Indonesian culture has historical roots, institutions, customs, values, and beliefs that many of its people share, but it is also a work in progress that is undergoing stresses at the beginning of the twenty-first century.

Indonesia is a nation with a diversity base on Pancasila with the philosophy of *Bhinneka Tunggal Ika*. If the diversity of Indonesia is managed well and maximum, it will be powerful and potentially great. On the contrary, if it is not managed properly then it will be a boomerang for Indonesia. Indonesia's diversity is like a double-edged blade. On the one hand, it will be a valuable potential, and, on the other hand, it will create conflicts which are capable to destroy the joints of national and state life and even the disintegration of the nation. *Bhinneka Tunggal Ika*'s philosophy which was initiated by the founding fathers of this nation aims to enable Indonesians to coexistence in a safe, peaceful, and prosperous environment. The pluralism of Indonesia society is seen from the perspective, action, and insight of everyone on various social, cultural, economic, political, and other phenomena. Indonesia society has diverse backgrounds in education, ethnicity, religion, social class, and economy, and has different views and actions on democracy, human rights, gender, and other social phenomena. Some members of society are less supportive of the democratization process, but there are some of them who support the democratization. Some members of the community are very concerned and fight for human rights, and some others are not; some even want to crush the rights of others.

The concept of multicultural integration in education is focused on understanding and appreciating students' own culture and the cultures of others, including religion, based on the motto *Bhinneka Tunggal Ika* (Unity in Diversity) and moral values of Pancasila. Multicultural integration in social studies' learning through Pancasila cultural values approach can adopt several principles, such as (1) Multicultural integration should be started from self of individual; (2) Multicultural integration should not develop ethnocentrism attitudes; (3) Multicultural integration can be developed in various aspects; (4) Multicultural integration must produce change; and (5) Multicultural integration must include social reality.

Method

This research was a qualitative research. Creswell (2010: 8) explained, "Qualitative research is an inquiry process of understanding based on distinct methodological traditions of inquiry that explore a social or human problem.

Approach and Subject Research

The research approach used an interpretive paradigm based on a type of qualitative approach. The research subjects (informants) were selected based on consideration of their reliability as informative sources. They were people who had really mastered the problems studied with multicultural condition. It may be futile to trace the next information to several other informants because there will be no new information that is different from that stated by the basic information. Conversely, if the informant is someone with less mastery of the research problem, then the other informants who dominate in the research problem must be explored while still referring to the problem under study (Gearon, 2002).

Data sources and procedures

The study used the sampling, or snowball, technique (sample selection in sequence). The data collection procedure involved three techniques, namely: (1) in depth interviews with basic informant (head of village and teacher of religious education); (2) participant observation, participants have characteristics, multi-ethnic school students Guardian, religious teachers, principals, and village heads; and (3) document study (Glasser & Strauss, 1967).

Data analysis

Descriptive qualitative analysis was employed. Analysis of the data was made by comparing or linking certain information with other information, which was done repeatedly to answer the questions that had been formulated in the research. The purpose of descriptive data analysis is to describe all the results in a field in a systematic and factual way. Such analysis is made through three step according to Miles and Huberman Theory : (1) data reduction, (2) data presentation and (3) conclusion (verification) (Miles et al., 2014).

Data Validity

Three criteria were used as the basis for checking the data in this study: degree of trust (credibility), dependability, and certainty (confirmability)

Results

The community of Pancasila Village (Balun Village, Turi, Lamongan, East Java) has a high degree of pluralism, influenced by the openness of the community, meaning that multicultural education is of high quality. The composition of official religious adherents in Indonesia which are embraced by the community is 50% Muslim, 30% Hindu, and 20% other faiths, which has consequences for the understanding of pluralism by the people, especially Muslims. Education in the community has different patterns and administrative arrangements with the conditions of implementation being within the scope of majority society.

Field observation studies show that communication between Muslims and other people has been running for a long time; since the beginning of the existence of Islam in the village there have plural demographic conditions,

encompassing various perspectives on different issues at the level of Islamic religious education. The villagers are tolerant and harmonious in a religious atmosphere, by the local people and well known as Pancasila Village. Harmony between religions has existed since the village was born until now.

In Pancasila village there is a mosque adjacent to the temple and church. The village is home to 3,780 Muslims, 688 Christians, and 282 Hindus. All the believers live in harmony and have firm principles, and all can perform their worship safely and comfortably. The ties of togetherness are particularly deeply felt when one of the religions commemorates a big day. For example, when Muslims celebrate IdulFitri, other people give congratulations and join in the celebrations. Rainer Forst formulates two conceptions of tolerance. The first is based on state authority (the permission concept), while the second is based on culture and the common will to build understanding and respect for others (the respect conception)(van den Brink & Owen, 2007). Based on the above issues, this study is entitled "Islamic Religious Education in Multicultural Communities in Pancasila Village Lamongan", with an emphasis on Islamic education in the formal path of the madrasah, as the basis for the research studies.

Findings on multicultural life are analysed to establish the meaning or essence underlying them. Subsequently, the findings are formulated into a theme form. Themes are the concepts of the theory presented by the data studied in research (Bogdan & Biklen, 2002). Such concepts and theories may either support, extend, or reject existing or emerging theories (Berman & Heyvaert, 1992). The research data indicate that the community, educational institutions, youth and community organizations, and the effectiveness of Islamic religious education affect the solution to multicultural problems. The facts derived from this study are discussed and adapted to Islamic education in multicultural villages.

The Role of Islamic Religious Education in the Multicultural Society of Pancasila Village

Society plays a very big role in and exerts an influence on the intellectual development and personality of learners. The community is a laboratory and a macro source full of alternatives to enrich the implementation of the educational process. Community members have a moral role and responsibility towards the implementation of this process. A reciprocal relationship between society and education is important for the advancement of education.

The life of religious communities, and the phenomena of religious life which are exclusive, textually normative and conservative, have contributed to the raising of contentious issues between religious believers in the world. The problems that arise in religious relationships, and the understanding of the fundamental doctrines of religion, is justified over all those human beings do. Human action that deviates from religious humanistic values can be the cause of clashes and battles, ethnic cleansing, as well as acts that deviate from the religious teachings put forward the passions and other interests as logical implications of the right.

The perception that religion is a disintegrative factor for mankind clearly deviates far from the ideals of normative religion. Religion is expected to solve all problems, on the contrary realized or not, construct the perception that religion is the strongest factor in the fight between humanity (destroyer). The above reality needs to polarize the problem to see it more objectively, as well as minimizing misperceptions in response to it.

Islamic religious education is closer to the reality of society than to the intersection (strengthening the doctrine of debilitating social solidarity). Religious education can greet poor and despicable people to cultivate a humanistic attitude and perspective on mankind, without the feeling that they are not part of us due to the strong formalization of religion in religious education to date. Such education should be completely overhauled. The educational process that upholds pluralism is an education that is suitable for daily life in Indonesia, and which from the beginning has presented religion on a moral-ethical basis, not on a basis, as in some countries, of making religion the official basis of state. The basis of idealistic conception in Islamic education is based on the Qur'an and hadith; it is a humanistic education with a pluralist ideology, with its own market in the middle of the nation that embraces the nation state. The scope of a more fundamental religious conception of education is "for you your religion, for me my religion". Islamic teaching offers a better conception of life.

The field results of previous research shows that the Pancasila community is a society that is open in accepting the presence of different ethnicity and other religions. The relationship between the Pancasila community and the outside community, both through political and economic relations and commerce, has made the society heterogeneous.

The reality of such heterogeneity encompasses almost all areas of society, including the economy, religion, and culture. The Pancasila village apparatus says that pluralism in the village began with the arrival of immigrants who brought their religious beliefs, which over time spread slowly to the local people.

Religious pluralism in the village was preceded by the existence of other communities, who married local people, through acculturation. Marriage is one path by which religious diversity, culture and ethnicity can emerge in certain areas. This is also confirmed by the following interview statement from head of village:

“The marriage notebooks that are with us (village modern) indeed contain some married inhabitants other than their religion. Most of the daughters (women) are locals, while other religions (Hindu, Christian) are on the male side ”.

Pancasila village (Muslim) is a dominant group. However, it provides space and freedom to other ethnic minorities to develop their culture and teachings. This is evident from the sense of brotherhood that occurs between religious leaders and children with different religious backgrounds, based on the values of local wisdom, such as polite behaviour in language and attitude.

The results of the field observations show the cooperation between the religious leaders and the people from different backgrounds in participating in clean village cooperation activities on the Sunday when the researcher arrived at the research location. Religious diversity has enriched Pancasila village culture, characterized by the social interaction among its multi-religious, Islamic, Christian, and Hindu people. Since the entry of Hinduism and Christianity in 1967 there has never been any religion-related conflict. Uniquely, there are no groupings of dwellings based on religion; they are mixed and evenly distributed.

Respect between religions in Pancasila Village is also seen in the implementation of each religion's activities. This form of respect is reflected in the following observations.

A sense of mutual respect is manifested during the holy month of Ramadan by followers of other religions. Hindus who are used to worshipping at 19:00, for example, are forced to change the schedule before Maghrib, as at 19.00+7 GMT Muslims are running tarawih prayers. The diversity of Pancasila villagers' beliefs has long been established, as each religious leader spreads the religion in the village. Of at least 1,500 households, 75% of Pancasila villagers are Muslim, 15% are Christian and the remaining 10% are Hindus. The respect and tolerance as described above are also confirmed from the interviews with Hindu religious leaders, as follows.

If the Nyepi holiday falls on a Friday, then the mosque does not directly use loudspeakers during Friday prayers, using only use a small loudspeaker, and the warning lights are turned off at night ".

Religion is the whole belief, and the doctrines of worship and the obligations associated with that belief, for the people of Pancasila. Development in the field of religion is very important and necessary, because its role determines the formation of a good character who believes in God Almighty, loves his or her neighbors, likes to do humanitarian activities, and is harmonious in social life.

Based on the results of the study document, Pancasila Village is one of the famous villages with the village of Pancasila. According to population data, there are three religions adopted; the Islam population is 3,807 inhabitants, 612 are Protestant Christians and Hindus number 284, with four places of worship: two mosques, one church and one pura, as well as other religious facilities such as the Islamic Dormitory School and Hindu religion and the other 7% followed by other religions.

Patterns of Religious Learning

The government officially recognizes six religions, namely Islam, Protestantism, Catholicism, Hinduism, Buddhism and Confucianism. With the many religions and beliefs that exist in Indonesia, inter-religious conflicts are often inevitable. Moreover, different patterns of religious teaching often trigger problems for its realization. Awareness of the religious differences that exist in the village of Pancasila is very high, as observed in the inter-religious harmony that exists in the community. The difference in religious education in each educational institution in the village plays a role in creating awareness of religious diversity. The role of the educational institutions in the village is also accompanied by the support of the people who have come down to maintain the differences in daily life, in behaviour, customs and culture. the role of educational institutions in accepting the religious differences of their respective adherents:

School institutional curriculum is a central curriculum combined with local content and self-development. The curriculum we apply in the KTSP (curriculum level of educational unit) in providing understanding to learners about the different religions adopted by our community is easy because we directly example to their neighbor who have different religion and the results they more understand directly about the application.

The creation of a conducive environment in terms of religious differences is not solely due to the existence of existing educational institutions in the village of Pancasila. In an interview, the village head of Pancasila explained that: "The role of educational institutions and community organizations and youth in Pancasila village, although it has a role in religious measurements but not 100%, but religious harmony in this village has been created since time immemorial, given that most Pancasila villagers originally embraced the Islam spread by Mbah Alun, but meantime Christian leaders entered the village and spread Christianity. The harmony between religions here has existed for a long time, together with the existence of educational institutions and community or educational organizations to accommodate the aspirations of the community and to provide education and continue their aspirations". The results of interviews and observations by researchers in the field show that the pattern of religious education, especially Islamic religious education in the village education institutions Pancasila can be seen that there is no special curriculum to support tolerance of religious diversity in Pancasila village.

Government

The active role of implementing policies needs power and authority, which will be used both to foster cooperation and to resolve any conflicts that may arise in the process. The means used can be persuasive (persuasive) and if necessary coercive. Without the element of coercion, the policy is only a statement of intent.

The mixture of culture that existed in the community has not been implicated to the village government, which also has implications for the implementation of Islamic teaching both in its implementation.

The role of government in the Pancasila village as the highest institution at the village level, especially in Pancasila village, is not played through a bureaucratic approach, but with a cultural approach. The village Head stated:

“We as head of the village and village government I can only safeguard the continuity of harmony in this village by continuing the previous traditions. There is no special program to accompany how to create harmony between the community and the existing religious teachings. It should be noted that the harmony in this village of Pancasila has existed since early days and the community already feels peaceful”.

Associated with the above, as the community from participant as student guardian statement as follows

"Religion is religion; a neighbour's relation with another neighbour or with the community is about the world. We need to differentiate beliefs, but we don't have to force them, if the neighbours in the community should respect each other".

The role of the village government, as exemplified by the above interviewees, is strengthened by the results of the research observations in the Pancasila village hall, indicating that the head office of the village office has several programs on display, but that there is no activity focusing on fostering religious harmony. From the above data, it can be concluded that the existence of the village government to implement village governance whose affairs with the community either administratively or institutionally, while religious issues are returned to the community as followers of their respective religions and religious leaders in the village.

Discussion

The Role of Islamic Education in Multicultural Society

The research results show that the role of religious education in building a multicultural society develops the values of Pancasila from the five precepts as the value of life. The influential people who bring commitment to the togetherness of the diverse community members of Pancasila village are (1) the community leaders; (2) village Head (3) the stakeholders/religious leaders and (4) the leaders of the village youth organizations. The roles of Islamic religious education in building a multicultural community in Pancasila village include (1) encouraging the implementation of religious harmony values among the same religious adherents in Pancasila Village; (2) fostering people's respective religious beliefs for mutual care and respect in activity-based places of worship, namely mosques, churches and temples; (3) encouraging youth organizations, including the *Miftahul Huda* Mosque Youth Organization, the GKJW Youth Organization, and the *Sweta Dharma* Organization for Hindus; (4) providing religious understanding and multicultural values in Islam; (5) socializing non-violent culture and respecting harmonious life in society and amongst students; (6) engendering a culture of solidarity, mutual understanding and respect in society and students; (7) instilling the value of mutual cooperation and help between people and students for togetherness, in order to create prosperity in the future; (8) instilling an understanding of the value of the alignment of rights and duties for everyone, even though people are from different tribes, religions and cultures, (9) apply the values of Pancasila, and the values of God, humanity, unity, democracy and justice in daily life; (10) inculcating anti-political jealousy by actualizing the values of healthy democracy in the life of the state and society; (11) developing cultural values which abide by the rules, upholding moral and ethical behaviour in the community, so as to create a harmonious social relationship between different religious or ethnic groups; and 12) giving encouragement to always create a sense of security, understanding and respect to allow all religious adherents to perform their daily social activities and religious services in accordance with the religion they believe in.

The results show that to achieve the goal of Islamic religious education in improving understanding of Islamic teachings, practicing skills, and improving the practice of Islamic teachings in everyday life. The goal of religious education is to become a Muslim with a sincere religious intensity, based on a strong faith.

The role relations Education with Horizontal Conflict that occurred in Indonesia is the impact of the failure of the education system to develop pluralism and multiculturalism. Religious education, as part of the national education system, is seen as the source of every riot, mental depravity, crime and all forms of social aberrations. It seems that this failure is because religious education is still in the process of transferring religious knowledge to students, but not the transformation of religious values to foster strong personalities and noble characters. The introduction of the religious curriculum and the enforced religious ethics have prompted academics to discuss the quality and content of religious education in schools (Fatih Genç et al., 2011).

The PAI curriculum requires change by showing the tolerant face of Islam, which can be explained from the point of view of the philosophies of perennialism, essentialism and progressiveness. The view of curriculum perennialism is the "construct" built to transfer what has happened in the past to the next generation for it to be conserved, passed on or developed. The perspective of progressive philosophy is that the curriculum should build future life, the present, and various national development plans to serve as a basis for developing future

lives. The principles of Islamic teaching are humanist, democratic and fair to learners. The principles that are very relevant to the future of the world are marked by the existence of cultural diversity and religion.

Therefore, the form of multicultural/intercultural education needs to be incorporated into the curriculum, but also needs to be developed and should not fall into simplistic multiculturalism. There is a clear role for specialists in religious education to contribute to the changing curriculum (Jackson, 2003). Schools teach religion in the form of dialogue, using interactive approaches and teaching materials that are not of a particular religion; they need to create a "multicultural laboratory" that will reward everyone, from any background, to and become inclusive schools which bridge the difference of culture.

Inter-Religious Relations in Building Multicultural Societies in Pancasila Village

The results of the research show that the pattern of inter-religious relationships in building a multicultural community in Pancasila village is based on (1) establishing relationships with values of tolerance; (2) creating non-interfering conditions among religious people, and citizens' consistency in creating a peaceful life; (3) following social customs which mutually respect neighbors; (4) preserving the traditions of the values of diversity inherited from generation to generation, to be guarded together according to the soul and values of Pancasila in the fifth in Pancasila; (5) ensuring all religious people in the village have the right to express their cultural identity democratically; (6) not marginalizing any particular cultural or religious identity, including the cultural identity of minority groups; (7) providing mutual help or cooperation in religious and social activities; (8) maintaining dialogue; (9) undertaking consecrated work; and (10) practicing mutual exposure, and being open to differences.

The condition of the community in the Pancasila village Turi, when analyzed according to Cultural Pluralism: A village of highly pluralistic individuals, with everyone and group identity able to live together and form a beautiful mosaic. Min (2002) argues that societies of individuals of different religious, ethnic, linguistic, and cultural backgrounds have the right to express their cultural identity democratically. However, the theory does not underestimate a cultural identity, including the cultural identity of minority groups. When in a society there are individuals who adhere to Islam, Catholicism, Protestantism, Hinduism, Buddhism and Confucianism, then all religious followers are given the opportunity to express their respective religious identity. Individuals in a society with a Javanese, Madurese, Betawi and Ambonese backgrounds, for example, are all entitled to show their cultural identity, even being allowed to develop it. A society that embraces this theory consists of highly pluralistic individuals, so that everyone and group identity can live together. Multicultural community research was also developed in the multicultural city of Hamburg, with the approach used in the form of interreligious learning, incorporating elements of religious and civic education (Weisse, 1996). A report on community cohesion concluded that a lack of communication in multicultural societies contributes to riots, and it is interesting for the promotion of intergroup dialogue a different culture and religion (Home Office, 2001).

Problems and Patterns of Solving Religious Education in Building the Multicultural Community of Pancasila Village, Balun Turi Lamongan

The results of the study show that there are various problems associated with religious education, including (1) the pattern of the learning of religion education in the classroom between the Muslim majority and other religious minorities, so the solution is the pattern of group learning implementation, which is grouping based on respective religions; (2) religious governance programs, which can cause sensitive inter-religious distrust if they are based on the value of religious morality and religion, and jointly carried out by people who have interfaith diversity. ; (3) the emergence of marriages between different religions, but in an effort to overcome obstacles, deliberation between families is facilitated by the government apparatus; and (4) the problem of media influence and external factors that can diminish the values of togetherness and tolerance among religious people, so that efforts to strengthen the strategic role of educational institutions and families as vehicles to preserve the culture of tolerance, harmony and cooperation between religious communities in the "Balun" village. The harmony is maintained and maintained so that this inter-religious and multiethnic harmony can be called the Pancasila village.

Effective instilling of values should be added to prevent the failure of religious education only as knowledge without practice. There are four factors relating to the failure of religious education to develop and instill pluralism and multiculturalism: first, the emphasis of religious education on the process of transfer of knowledge from the process of transformation of religious knowledge and religious values to students; second, the attitude of government and education actors who regard religious education as a "mere curriculum appendix"; third, the lack of emphasis on moral values that support interreligious harmony, such as love, compassion, friendship, tolerance and peace; and fourth, the lack of attention to studying other religions.

The teaching of Islamic religion in schools should contain a curriculum based on diversity. Islamic religious education given to students does not create a single understanding, but an educational curriculum that can support the student and guidance process the process of being democratic, pluralist and emphasizing real life to become a complete human being. The curriculum must include subjects such as tolerance, inclusive *Aqidah*, *Fiqh Muqarran* and religious comparisons and themes on ethno-cultural and religious differences; the danger of discrimination; conflict resolution and mediation; human rights, democracy and plurality; universal humanity;

and other relevant subjects. This would be a curriculum capable of delivering learners an interreligious dialogue, tackling theological issues and engaging faith, because true dialogue is impossible without entering theological issues and involving faith. Therefore, ultimately every Muslim will be able to do what Dunne (1978) calls "passing over, passing from one culture to another, from one way of life to another, and from one religion to another. This is followed by a similar and opposite process called "coming back", returning with new insight into our own culture, way of life, and religion itself. Research on intercultural education relationships and the challenge of religious diversity and dialogue was approved by the education committee in this village (Council of Europe, 2003; Jackson, 2003).

Conclusion and Implications

Interreligious Relationships in Building the Multicultural Community of Pansacila village

The patterns of interaction and interreligious relationships in building multicultural communities in Pancasila village are (1) building relationships with values of tolerance; (2) creating non-interfering conditions among religious communities, and the consistency of citizens in creating a peaceful life; (3) maintaining customs; (4) preserving the traditions of differentiated values that are passed down from generation to generation, to be guarded together according to the souls and values of the five *sila* of Pancasila; (5) allowing all religious people in the village the right to express their cultural identity democratically; (6) not marginalizing any particular cultural or religious identity, including the cultural identity of minority groups; (7) providing mutual help or cooperation in religious and social activities; (8) maintaining dialogue; (9) partaking in consecration; and (10) allowing mutual exposure and openness to differences.

Problems and Patterns of Solving Religious Education in the Multicultural Community of Pancasila village

The problems of religious education are (1) the learning patterns of religious education in the classroom between the Muslim majority and other religious minorities, with the pattern of group teaching grouped according to respective religions; (2) religious governance programs can cause sensitivity if they are based on the budget of religious morality and religion, so that the government program is not based on religious but more social and developmental development, for the religious activities done by the youth organization and implemented together with the interfaith community; (3) the emergence of marriage between different religions, but as an effort to overcome obstacles, the deliberation between families is facilitated by the government apparatus; (4) the problem of media influence and external factors that can diminish the values of togetherness and tolerance between religious people, so that efforts to strengthen the strategic role of educational institutions and families as vehicles to preserve the culture of tolerance, harmony and cooperation between religious communities in the village remain in the guard and preserved with Pancasila village.

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Author Information

Sutiah Sutiah

Departement of Islamic Education, Faculty of
 Tarbiyah and Teaching Training, Universitas Islam
 Negeri (UIN) Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang,
 Gajayana 50, Malang 65144, Indonesia
